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Multifunctional Composites for Energy Harvesting

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CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

PZT/SMPU
Piezoelectric
Composites

Shape Memory
Polyurethanes(SMPU)
Material

Lead Zirconate
Titanate(PZT)
Piezoelectric Material

Vehicle

Aerospace

Shape Memory
Effect

Medical

Textile

Traditional Flexible Piezoelectric Energy Harvester Composite

Traditional Flexible Energy Harvester

Nanotubes or wires

Nanoparticles or thin films

Nanofibers

Most Issue

**Flexibility
Feel
Comfort**

Preparation

Coating Electrodes

Shape-memory Property

Bending

Recovery

$$\text{Recovery Rate} = \frac{\text{Maximum Displacement} - \text{Residue Displacement}}{\text{Maximum Displacement}}$$

Materials	Recovery rate (%)		
	1 st Cycle	2 st Cycle	3 st Cycle
SMPU	90.88	94.42	96.22
Modified 60%	89.16	94.72	95.98
Modified 70%	87.39	95.39	97.62
Modified 80%	86.15	94.71	97.09

Energy Harvesting

Summary

Active flexible electrode

Smart glove

Actuator

Touch sensor

Energy harvester

Shape Memory Effect

PZT/SMPU
Piezoelectric
Composite

Flexible
Textile
Structure

Piezoelec
tricity

Health monitoring

Wearable devices

Automobile parts

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